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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

FROM EARTHQUAKES TO AN APENNINE SIBYL AND
A LAKE OF PONTIUS PILATE:
A NEW CONJECTURE ON THE ORIGIN OF THE
LEGENDARY TRADITION OF THE SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN
RANGE IN ITALY¹

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1. Seismic land and generation of legends

Earthquakes and ancient legendary tales: could it be that the peculiar seismic character of a territory may have inspired attempts by antique local populations to develop prescientific accounts on the origin of shocks and tremblors, involving the elaboration of oral narratives aimed at providing a mythical explanation as to the generation of earthquakes?

This is what possibly occurred, in times as ancient as the Iron Age, at the very center of pre-Roman Italy: the elaboration by Sabines and Picenes of a complex legendary structure, unfolding across many centuries, which was shaped to deal with tremblor-induced terror and involved the definition of rituals aimed at protecting local settlements from recurrent seismic destruction. A legendary structure which is now totally lost to us, but whose faint remnants are still visible and readable in later unexplained legendary narratives, whose original meaning is to be unveiled according to this new original, conjectural scenario.

The seismic land which has repeatedly been struck by earthquakes over the millennia is the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines; and the renowned, unexplained legendary narratives which have inhabited the same region for many centuries, possibly shielding from view an earlier legendary framework connected to earthquakes, are the ancient tales concerning the Sibyl's Cave and the Pilate's Lake.

Fig. 1 - Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

This new, unprecedented conjecture was set forth by Italian physicist and writer Michele Sanvico in a series of papers released on Academia.edu and Researchgate.net from 2017 to 2020. A reasoned, consistent research which casts a new light on the illustrious legendary framework which lives amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountains and was once widely known throughout Europe.

As fully highlighted by the researcher, the fifteenth-century tales which are retrieved in Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, connected to the presence of an Apennine Sibyl concealed beneath the cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range, and Antoine de la Sale's account *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, which narrates of both a sibilline subterranean kingdom and a demonic Lake which allegedly houses the burial place of Pontius Pilate, are not of local origin: they both came from distant lands and settled in a specific location in central Italy where possibly older legends were present already.

Both are to be considered as literary layers which seem to have been superimposed to a basic mythical core connected to the presence of a sinister Cave and Lake on what is known today as Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore.

2. *The Sibyl that wasn't there*

A main starting point in the investigation of the origin of the legendary tale of an Apennine Sibyl set on Mount Sibyl, in the Italian mountainous region set between the provinces of Umbria and Marche, is the fact that, before the fifteenth century, we cannot retrieve any previous literary reference about an oracular Sibyl who allegedly lived in that area of the central Apennines².

Nothing is reported about the presence of a Sibyl in the *Reductorium Morale* written by Petrus Berchorius, a French monk and abbot, at the mid of the fourteenth century, a work in which he mentions the sinister renown of a magical Lake of Norcia, yet no words are spent on a sibilline abode laying in the same area; and no reference to any Sibyls is contained in the verses written in fourteenth-century *Dittamondo* by Fazio degli Uberti, a

2 Sanvico M., *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, 2018, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007820

poet from Tuscany, on a gloomy mount and Lake of Pilatus. And no Sibyl is mentioned, either, in the *Charters of the Municipality and People of the Land of Norcia* (*Statuti del Comune et Populo della Terra di Norcia*), a collection of laws and rules dating to the same century.

If we push ourselves further back, we jump straight (owing to the lack of any other relevant references) to the fourth century, with Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius and his *De divinis institutionibus adversus gentes*, in which the Latin author enumerates a list of ten Sibyls, considered by scholars as a classical standard catalogue: however, only three are the Sibyls connected to Italy (the Cumaean, the Cimmerian and the Tiburtine). And it can be easily determined, from a number of well-known literary references, that no one of them features any relation to the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Even the Tabula Peutingeriana, which comes to us from the times when the Roman Empire was a ruling power, makes available no information on a possible sibilline site in the region set between the ancient provinces of Picenum and the river Tiber. The specific area in the Tabula where the Sibillini Mountain Range raises its peaks appears to be empty.

Fig. 2 - The area of today's Sibillini Mountain Range in the Tabula Peutingeriana (Codex Vindobonensis no. 324, Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek, Wien)

So the legendary tale which concerns a Sibyl of the Apennines seems to pop up from a sort of literary void at the beginning of the fifteenth century: a sign that the investigation into the tale's origin must take a different course, if we really want to fill that void.

3. *The Apennine Sibyl as an extraneous legend*

The Sibyl who, according to Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, allegedly found an abode in the Sibillini Mountains, Italy, actually originates from a most illustrious literary lineage, as she is connected to the characters of Morgan le Fay and her companion Sebile, who both belong to the Matter of Britain; this is a connection that can be fully retraced across an extended collection of medieval romances and poems staging the two necromancers and their magical, concealed realms³.

As a matter of fact, 'Sibyl' is a traditional character that is often present within the romances and poems belonging to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle. Her first appearance in written literature as a powerful necromancer, just as powerful as Morgan le Fay, King Arthur's half-sister, and with a potential reference to Vergil's Cumaean Sibyl, dates back to 1185 and the poem *Erec*, written by German poet Hartmann von Aue. From that time on, in many medieval works Sibyl began to be staged as Morgan's companion and best friend, with an increasing confusion and mix-up between the figures of the two enchantresses.

Lechery, captivity of knights, and magical dwellings set beneath castles and mountains, in one case raising even in Italy, were all characters attached to Morgan across a number of works, including *Li Hauz Livres di Graal*, *Parzival*, *Lestoire de Merlin*, *Le Livre d'Artus*, *Claris et Laris*, *Floriant et Florète*, *Ly Myreur des Histors*. Following von Aue's *Erec* and an incessant flow of oral narratives, the same traits were also conferred to Morgan's companion, Sebile, staged jointly with her fellow-enchantress as in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, *Prophécies de Merlin* and *La Chanson d'Esclarmonde*, or even as a principal character as in *Wartburgkrieg* and *Perceforest*: an unrelenting journey across the centuries, which also includes *Huon de Bordeaux*, in which a lady called Sebile lives in a

3 Sanvico M., *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*, 2019, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007828, 4007836

magical castle guarded by metal contrivances similar to the enchanted doors mentioned by Antoine de la Sale, and *Huon d'Auvergne*, featuring a necromantic dame who lives under a mountain.

Fig. 3 - The passage on «Sebile l'enchanteresse» from the *Prophécies de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 25434, British Library, folium 173r)

A complete list of literary references including a significant number of mentions of the character and deeds of 'Sebile', the powerful enchantress staged in many chivalric poems and romances which are part of the Matter of Britain, is presented in the dedicated paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*, fully supporting the inference that the narrative which concerns an Apennine Sibyl is not original of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as it has to be considered as an offspring of this illustrious, extraneous, northern-European literary tradition.

The above scenario seems to point straight to a transplant of a version of the story of Morgan and Sebile into the remote peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range: a mountainous chain which seemed fit enough, for some unspecified reasons, to host a legendary narrative centered on a necromantic Sibyl housed in a Cave set beneath a rocky crest. A Sibyl that was not born there, as it is now clear that she belongs to a different mythical tradition coming from northern, far-off countries.

The Sibyl of the Apennines as an offspring of the negromantic character of 'Sebile' widely present in the Matter of Britain: though overlooked by most of the researchers who across the decades have confronted with the specific issue concerning Mount Sibyl, this relationship was already highlighted in the past by illustrious academics (Lucy Ann Paton, Ferdinando Neri, Roger S. Loomis) without turning into the principal focus of their investigations. Time has come now to fully address this fascinating topic and push the enquiry further ahead along a path that will lead to significant findings.

4. Pontius Pilate as an extraneous legend

In the Sibillini Mountain Range, a few miles away from Mount Sibyl and the alleged abode of an apennine oracle, lies another arcane geographical setting: a Lake set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, whose name was connected to the figure of Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Judaea from 26 A.D. to 36 A.D., an official of the Roman Empire who played a key role in the Passion of Jesus Christ. The Lake is considered by tradition as the prefect's cursed resting place, as attested by Antoine de la Sale in his work, with his lively and ghastly description of a chariot drawn by buffaloes rushing straight into the icy waters of the Lake together with the prefect's body.

However, as it is fully known to scholars, the tradition concerning the legendary fate of Pontius Pilate was not born here: a vast number of literary witnesses exist, across Europe and over many centuries, which tell the tale of the ultimate resting place of the Roman prefect, a tale which has no connection with the Italian Apennines⁴.

After reading the words that were written on Pilate by classical authors such as Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria, and, of course, the passages which mention Pilate in the canonical Gospels, the main line of investigation follows the works of the Fathers of the Church who, since the earliest centuries of Christianity, addressed a tricky issue: did Pilate actually make substantial efforts to set Jesus free from the accusations that were made against him by the Jews? Or, did he eventually leave the Son of God to his doom of death on the Cross? Across the centuries, different

⁴ Sanvico M., *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate* (2019), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4008243, 4008248, 4008254

answers were pronounced which led to consider the Roman prefect either as a saint or a servant to the Evil.

During the centuries of the Middle Ages many apocryphal works on Pontius Pilate, including the *Epistola Pilati*, the *Gesta Pilati*, the *De Vita Pilati*, the *Anaphora Pilati*, the *Paradosis Pilati*, the *Legenda Aurea* and others), used to circulate throughout Europe, certainly arising from a mesh of oral tales which were narrated before fascinated audiences belonging to all social classes, and attracting ever-growing legendary accounts on his life, deeds, final prosecution by an almost Christianised Emperor, be it Tiberius or Vespasian, and final death.

This collection of tales on Pilate also provided many details on his ultimate resting place as well. Actually, there was more than one single resting place. And all such places were infested by demons. Be it the Tiber in Rome, or the river Rhône by the French town of Vienne, or a marsh or a pit in the Swiss Alps, the fiendish corpse of Pontius Pilate was not to find any rest: demons awaited his arrival and rejoiced in his company, arousing storms and tempests at the very spot of the prefect's burial.

Fig. 4 - The corpse of Pilate is finally thrown into an abyss amid the mountains (the words 'pit' and 'montibus' are highlighted) in the *Legenda Aurea* from manuscript NAL 1747, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (folium 93v)

This is no different from what Antoine de la Sale narrated in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, dating to the first half of the fifteenth century: in the vicinity of Mount Sibyl, a Lake of Pilate housed exactly the same story, with the addition of a chariot and buffaloes, a canonical image of the Triumph of Death. And his story portrays the same sort of tempests.

However, not a single manuscripted work belonging to the medieval tradition on the cursed burial place of Pilate ever mentions the Apennines or the region around Mount Sibyl as one of Pontius Pilate's haunted resting places.

The legendary narration is certainly the same, but the Lakes of Pilate and the Sibillini Mountain Range do not seem to be part of it. Especially when we consider that the earliest retrievable mention about our Italian Lake, as found in Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale*, does report about the presence of demons, but at the same time does not provide any mention of the name of Pilate.

Therefore, it is easily inferred that the legend was not born here: as a matter of fact, it was transplanted to this place, deeply set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, as an extraneous mythical material. And the myth was possibly transferred to this location around the beginning of the second half of the fourteenth century, a date which is pointed to by the peculiar presence of the chariot and buffaloes, a possible iconographic reference to the plague that ravaged Italy and Europe after the year 1347, with the chariots being used for the transportation of corpses.

5. A fundamental question: why right here?

As a result of the preceding investigation, we find ourselves with a complex of legendary tales which lives amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines at the center of the peninsula. The tales are connected to a Cave (an Apennine Sibyl on the top of Mount Sibyl) and a Lake (the resting place of Pontius Pilate on the top of Mount Vettore).

However, we are now certain that the two tales, mutually independent though living a few miles away from each other, were not born here.

The Sibyl of the Apennines comes down from a similar character fully belonging to the Matter of Britain: Sebile, the necromancer, friend and alterego of Morgana. And Pontius Pilate, with his demonic burial place, is

rooted in the well-known medieval tradition concerning the fate of the Roman prefect and the many graves for his cursed corpse.

The two independent, mutually unrelated tales appear to have both settled in the same area, the Sibillini Mountain Range. They colonized a Cave and a Lake set only a few miles away from each other, and began to enjoy a significant renown from the fifteenth century onwards, with visitors coming to the two sites from all over Europe, looking for the hidden realm of a sensual Sibyl and in search of a demonic place for the consecration of spellbooks, as attested by many literary witnesses across the subsequent centuries.

Philological research, which started on the subject at the end of the nineteenth century, soon had to confront with questions which seemed to be unanswerable. Nobody, amid the many scholars who have been dealing with the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary heritage, could figure out the possible reasons that led so illustrious, extraneous tales, which were born elsewhere, to settle down amid these remote fastnesses, certainly not a prominent location in Italy.

Fig. 5 - A vision of the Sibillini Mountain Range showing the positions of the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave

Why did a Sibyl and a Roman prefect, belonging to heterogeneous, unrelated legendary traditions, come and deposit themselves right into the position marked by these distant Italian mountains, like balls spinning on a roulette wheel? What sort of unidentified local factor, possibly linked to any peculiar nature of this region, was so remarkable as to generate a powerful mythical attraction for highly-emotional legendary narratives coming from foreign territories and traditions?

Can we provide any answer to such questions? Yes, because if we proceed further into our investigation and lift the fog cast on the whole matter by the presence of medieval, extraneous layers we may get a glimpse of what lies beyond.

And what lies beyond appears to be an older, almost-forgotten, original legendary tale.

6. A legend before the legends

If we remove the two literary layers concerning an Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate, which are to be considered as additional legendary overlays, and we start to look attentively into the underlying characters of the legends which mark the two sites, the Cave and the Lake in the Sibillini Mountain Range, we get glimpses of some sort of different narrative: a narrative that was already there; a narrative that had nothing to do with Sibyls and antique Roman prefects. Something that seems to preexist the two additional, extraneous legendary layers.

Some older legend, lying underneath, seems to have attracted the two illustrious tales of Sebile/Morgan and Pilate to the Sibillini Mountains; and traces of it can be found in certain common features which can be retrieved within the Cave's and Lake's traditions, just below the visible layers which stage a Sibyl of the Apennines and a first-century Roman prefect.

A thorough investigation of the available sources shows that common, original traits can be highlighted with relation to the two distinct tales which concern the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate: both legends feature a number of shared aspects, namely the performance of necromantic rituals

at the two sites, the presence of legendary demons at the Cave and Lake, and devastation and tempests oddly arising from both places when necromancy is performed, as reported by many authors from the fourteenth century onwards. All listed aspects are thoroughly highlighted in literature and analysed in a specific, dedicated paper⁵.

The first and second shared aspects both point to some sort of magical, supernatural, legendary presences which may have found an abode under the Lake's icy waters and in the inner recesses of the Cave; the third trait, which relates to an odd, puzzling phenomenon originating from the Cave and Lake, i.e. the raising of tempests that would allegedly sweep and ravage the surrounding land, is a feature that has always been completely overlooked by scholars; on the contrary, it makes up a most significant piece of information when considered in the light of a comprehensive enquiry into the true origin of the legendary narratives which live in the Sibillini Mountain Range, as we will see later in this same paper.

Necromancy, demonic presence, raising of tempests; and a fourth common element is also extant: the marks of the presence of some sort of otherworldly passageway.

Fig. 6 - A miniature from a *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal*, a French manuscripted version of the *Vision of Tnugdalus* dating to 1475 and preserved at the Getty Museum

5 Sanvico M., *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* (2019), doi:10.5281/zenodo.4008256

Amid the most remarkable elements that the Sibillini Mountain's tradition received from earlier otherworldly accounts we find the magical 'test bridge'⁶, narrow as a razor's edge but widening itself when trodden by a true, righteous soul, a narrative item which is part of a most renowned literary tradition spanning through Europe across a thousand years, and throughout the Middle Ages; and the magical ever-slamming doors⁷, a metal device which is retrieved in a number of different forms in many chivalric romances and poems: a narrative legacy which comes from very antique times, and can ultimately be traced in Vergil's *Aeneid* (the gates of Tartarus) and Apollonius of Rhodes' *Argonautica* (the Symplegades).

Fig. 7 - A seventeenth-century print showing the ship Argo as it passes through the clashing rocks of Symplegades, preserved at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York

6 Sanvico M., *Antoine de la Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl* (2018), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007737

7 Sanvico M., *The literary truth about the magical doors in "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl"* (2018), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007743

These are literary items which seem to mark the presence of an otherwordly narrative. Has the Sibillini Mountain Range ever been considered as a possible passageway to some sort of Otherworld in a remote past?

The answer might be in the affirmative, because as we proceed further into our investigation we find a number of patent narrative links to other renowned tales concerning classical and medieval journeys into the Otherworld, including Vergil's *Aeneid*, with the Cumaean Hades; St. Patrick's Purgatory at Lough Derg, Ireland; and various early-Christian and medieval visions accounting for legendary visits to a realm of the dead or a demonic Hell, as we will see in the next paragraph.

7. The Lake and Cave: entryways to an otherwordly realm

We believe that the correct path we need to tread if we want to unveil the true core of the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range leads to a specific, and somewhat unexpected, keyword: Otherworld⁸.

Otherworld: a most ancient dream that men have been dreaming since the earliest antiquity when confronting with life and death, mortality and the divine, and, after the rise of the Christian era, the ultimate truths of salvation and punishment.

At a closer scrutiny, the legendary tales of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate appear to be marked by a number of otherwordly narrative elements. In the account written by Antoine de la Sale, a test bridge of supernatural narrowness crosses a frightful abyss, but it gets wider as you tread on it, a typical contrivance dating back to Pope Gregory the Great's *Dialogues* and then present in a number of medieval visionary writings. Metal doors are also present, magically slamming day and night with a ceaseless crushing motion, a sort of device which is found in earlier chivalric works and is connected to otherwordly descriptions contained in the *Aeneid* and in the Greek myth of the Symplegades. Crystal rooms await the visitors in the Sibyl's Cave, the clear sign of an afterlife setting. And the Lake is openly

⁸ Sanvico M., *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld* (2020), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4008259, 4008261

indicated as an entrance to Hell in an excerpt drawn from Petrus Berchorius, written in the fourteenth century. The Lake itself is called 'Lake Avernus' in a manuscripted diagram dating to the sixteenth century, thus marking a remarkable narrative correspondance with the famous, classical entryway to the House of Hades set in Cumae.

Fig. 8 - The Lakes set in the Sibillini Mountain Range as depicted in the sixteenth-century diagram found in manuscript Vat Lat 5241 (folium 9v)

An entryway to the Otherworld: since time immemorial this has been an impious craving housed in the soul of men. A dream, a desire for a vision of the afterlife, a longing for prohibited communications with the dead, a quest for obtaining forbidden wishes. And the search for an ultimate truth.

A well-established Western tradition narrates the ghastly journeys performed by visionary heroes in otherworldly realms. In classical antiquity, Ulysses and his visit to Hades, then Aeneas and his journey into the Avernus, with the Cumaean Sibyl as a guide. And subsequently, the visions of early Christianity: St. Paul and his visionary dreams of Hell, Pope St. Gregory I the Great with his soldier, the first in a series of knights travelling to the Otherworld. And, then again, Ireland, with its medieval descriptions of appalling journeys into the excruciating torments and punishments inflicted to the sinners: the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, the *Vision of Tnugdalus*, and the *Purgatory of St. Patrick*.

But only two are the journeys that are utterly special, the travels into the Otherworld par excellence: these are travels that are performed not in a mere vision, but in actual reality. With a man's physical body.

In the Western literary tradition, two are the most renowned places on Earth where to initiate such a horrifying travel. Two 'hot spots'. Two crevices pierced in the continuity of our ordinary world. Two fissures, dreadfully opened to legendary physical visions of a subterranean, chthonian Hell.

The first is at Cumae, by the Lake Avernus, in southern Italy. And the second is at the Purgatory of St. Patrick, Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, in northern Ireland.

At those two sites, living men could be so fool as to make an attempt at crossing the gates which must never be crossed. Two passageways to the Otherworld. Two entryways to an afterlife inhabited by legendary demonic powers.

The two traditional entrances were widely known throughout the Middle Ages and across the entire Europe. They had been the subjects of many literary works, from the *Aeneid* to the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* and the *Legenda Aurea*. People engaged themselves in difficult journeys as far as the two listed locations with the aim to see, and cross, the contact points between two worlds, which are normally separated: the world of the living, and the realm of the dead.

Fig. 9 - The Lake of Avernus, Cumae, Italy

By an odd chance, not due to any specific, traceable reason, both sites were indicated by the same pair of landmarks: a lake and a cave for both, two landforms which fully identified the two sites on the surface of Earth, and were known as such.

Why Cumae and Lough Derg? Why did passageways to the Otherworld happen to settle exactly in those two locations? Caves were in the volcanic soil of Cumae, that were filled to the vaulted ceilings with mephitic gases, which induced dreams, and sometimes a horrible death. A cave was also to be found at Lough Derg: on entering, sleep overwhelmed the already exhausted pilgrims, who then dreamt and had nightmares, possibly out of the lack of breathable air, and, maybe, owing to the presence of poisonous gases arising from the marshy ground.

Fig. 10 - Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland

Lake Avernus and its cave at Cumae. Lough Derg and its cave in Ireland. But a third set of landmarks, similarly made up by a Lake and a Cave, was possibly present in central Italy as well. It was the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range. Set only a few miles away from each other.

The same geographical configuration, as at Cumae and Lough Derg. A demonic presence registered and necromantic rituals being performed at this third Italian site, too. Otherworldly traits, which marked the two landforms amid the Apennines, too.

Many narrative resonances can be traced between the legendary tradition which lives amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range and Cumae on one side, and between the mountains of the Sibyl and Lough Derg on the other side.

In the fifteenth-century romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, it is the Apennine Sibyl herself, endowed with oracular powers as the Cumaean prophetess, who proclaims her identification with the Cumaean Sibyl in front of the valiant knight Guerrino: «I want you to know my name. I was called 'Cumaean' by the Romans for I was born in a town in the countryside whose name is Cumae». And this legendary link to the Cumaean Sibyl remains visible through the subsequent centuries: less than a hundred years later, the Cumaean origin of the Apennine Sibyl is mentioned by Ludovico Ariosto as well, with the following words included in his poem *Orlando Furioso*: «[...] the Cumæan Sibyl [...] who fled, in antiquity, to a Cavern in the territory of Norcia», with a further connection referenced in the same poetical work («... be it at the Lake Avernus, or at the caves by Norcia...»). A further, unequivocal links can be retrieved in the sixteenth-century diagram found in manuscript Vat Lat 5241, in which the Lake set in the Sibillini Mountain Range is called 'Lake Avernus'.

As to Lough Derg, narrative affinities can be manifestly found between Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea*, which its account of a descent into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, and *Guerrino the Wretch* with its visit to the Sibyl's abode, with the same invocations raised by the respective heroes to ask for divine protection, the same 'test bridge' staged by all three authors (and by Antoine de la Sale as well) in the subterranean regions, and a full section devoted by Andrea da Barberino to a journey into St. Patrick's Purgatory made by his knight Guerrino, immediately following his successful escape from the Sibyl's Cave. And another ghastly connection can be found, as we read the words contained in Gerald of Wales' *Topographia Hibernica* which describe the demons at the lake of St. Patrick's Purgatory ravaging the bodies of the unwary visitors: the same

treatment that awaits the men that are cast into the Lake of Norcia as depicted by Petrus Berchorius in his *Reductorium morale*.

Thus the many similarities which are manifestly found among the three sites, Cumae, Lough Derg and the Sibillini Mountain Range, all including a lake and a cave and a local otherworldly tradition, appear to have fostered many narrative contaminations, mainly from the two most famous ones to the less known Apennine site. Across many centuries, local residents, wayfarers, oral storytellers and men of letters spread the word about this amazing Lake and Cave concealed amid the ridges of the central Apennines, in Italy, by adding to their wondrous accounts a number of narrative elements taken from the famed legendary tales of the Cumaean Sibyl and St. Patrick's Purgatory, also marked by lakes and caves.

The nature of this connection between the three sites is merely narrative, as no actual, specific historical link has ever existed between the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, on one side, and the legendary tales concerning Cumae and the Purgatory of St. Patrick, on the other. The three locations were too far from each other to develop any common, coordinated legendary framework. Their respective lores were totally independent from one another. Just an overall affinity, though patently manifest, linked the three places together: presence of a lake, presence of a cave, and the existence of a legendary physical passageway to an Otherworld, which attracted visitors, be they pilgrims or necromancers.

So all the clues seem to indicate that in this third, specific location of Europe, amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, by a Lake and a Cave, mortal beings like Aeneas, like Owein, may have made actual attempts to access a different world, normally forbidden to the living: a realm of dead souls, a kingdom which was set under the rule of non-human entities, of a divine, terrifying nature. A chthonian, subterranean Otherworld.

In this promising research framework, a number of questions can be stated: why should this Apennine site have been considered as a further entryway to the Otherworld? If the above assumption were true, what kind of Otherworld was this? What sort of dreadful dreams did men conceive by the Lake and Cave set on the mountains of the Apennines, in central Italy?

A passageway to some sort of demonic presence. An access that was to be unlocked by means of necromantic rituals. A point of contact with a subterranean Otherworld. A 'hot spot', a crevice drilled into the mountains to establish an appalling communication with the chthonian powers beneath. A break in the continuum of our ordinary world, providing an access to a forbidden, inhuman realm.

«Descendunt in infernum viventes»: «they descend alive into Hell», so wrote Petrus Berchorius in his fourteenth-century *Reductorium Morale*, quoting from the Book of Psalms. He was writing about the Lake of Norcia, in the Sibillini Mountain Range⁹.

Fig. 11 - A descent into Hell, the Lake of Norcia, as taken from the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (manuscript Latin 16786, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 301v)

So, the resulting, far-reaching assumption which arises from our research is that a legendary passageway to some sort of Otherworld might have been possibly situated, by an antique tradition that left faint traces in the known literature, among the peaks of central Apennines.

This is the basis of our new supposition: the possible existence of a legendary credence concerning an entryway to a mythical Otherworld in central Italy. One of a most terrific, dreadful sort. A crevice in our world, opened in the mountainous ridges out of sheer terror. Terror for one own's life. Terror for the fate of one's family. Terror for the ruin of one's land.

Because according to the new conjecture proposed by the author of the present paper, the nature of this sibilline Otherworld is closely linked to the intrinsic nature of this Apennine territory, and to a very specific, blood-curdling word. A word which has always unleashed the deepest fears of human soul, since the earliest antiquity.

And this word is earthquake.

⁹ Sanvico M., *The Lake of Pilatus in an antique manuscript: Pierre Bersuire and the fourteenth-century dark renown of Norcia's lake* (2018), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007806

8. Earthquakes as the key to legends

Following a thorough perusal of the available literary sources, a significant connection can be established between earthquakes and the local legendary tradition which inhabits the Sibillini Mountains, in the Italian Apennines¹⁰.

Fig. 12 - The hamlet of Castelluccio di Norcia sitting on hill before Mount Vettore, wrecked by the earthquakes in 2016

The Sibillini Mountain Range is a land of mighty earthquakes. Its peculiar seismic character, marked by the presence of active, colliding fault lines, is prominent when compared to other areas in Italy. The region was struck by destructive earthquakes in 2016; seismic devastations occurred in 1979, 1859, 1730, 1703 (one of the most powerful tremblors ever occurred in Italy), 1328; references to earlier frightful blows are retrieved in Roman literature. The effects of historical earthquakes can be seen today on the very face of the Sibillini mountains, including the large scar that runs

¹⁰ Sanvico M., *Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend* (2020), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4008263, 4008265

across the western side of Mount Vettore. And several physical effects were produced on the land and patently made visible by the 2016 seismic shocks, with the appearance of fractures, holes, displacements across the versants and valleys. In addition, seismic tremors always accompany local people's everyday life, with small shocks and short sequences of faint tremblors occurring all year long, easily perceived in the stillness of the night. And the acoustic effects of the most powerful earthquakes, like the one that occurred in 2016, are utterly hair-raising: according to local witnesses, the very mountains appear to scream and yell as a wounded, demonic beast.

Fig. 13 - The giant fault line which runs across Mount Vettore

In modern times scientific knowledge supports us in controlling our fears of men living in the twenty-first century. On the contrary, across the Iron Age, no rational knowledge, no scientific explanation was available to the local populations of Sabines and Picenes to account for earthquakes and the terror unleashed by land shaking. They could only resort to myth, with the generation of appropriate legendary narratives. So a conjecture can be put forth that some rituals might have been performed at the two geographical landmarks, the Cave on the top of Mount Sibyl and the Lake set within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, not far from one another, in a tentative — and actually hopeless — effort carried out by local populations to establish a dreadful communication link with the mighty chthonian potencies, of a demonic nature, who were concealed beneath the ground: fiendish beings who supposedly lived under the mountains and, in people's opinion, possibly presided over the earthquakes.

Archeological campaigns carried out in the Italian provinces of Umbria, Marche and Latium during the last thirty years have shown that Sabines and Picenes used to dedicate highland shrines — small sites marked by the presence of votive deposits and placed in selected locations on hilltops, mountain-sides, water springs and along main trails — to the worship of local deities: a specific mark of the culture and territorial presence of the populations which inhabited the Apennines during the Iron Age.

Fig. 14 - Small bronze statues of warriors dating to the fifth century B.C. found in the votive deposit at the highland shrine of Ancarano of Norcia (Vatican Museums)

So it can be conjecturally envisaged that highland shrines might have been established at the Lake and Cave too, on the elevated locations where Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore raise their cliffs. Offerings and other rituals could have been performed at both sites in ancient times.

Fig. 15 - The crowned peak of Mount Sibyl

It can be imagined that the elderly in local communities possibly used to bequeath to the younger generations a collection of tales about their forefathers, who had been struck by the earthquakes in earlier times and had seen the mountains yell and rupture. They had ascended the cliffs to implore the mercy of the mountains themselves, the abode where the demons lived. They knew that some sort of fiendish being or beings resided under the rocky peaks. And the Lake and Cave, both being impressive landmarks set amid elevated crests, were possibly considered as suitable points of access to the demonic Otherworld: locations where a supernatural communication between human beings and vicious deities was reputed to be conceivable.

The whole set of religious credences concerning the earthquakes was possibly wiped out from the region by the subsequent Roman conquest (third century B.C.). Romans basically embraced Aristotle's prescientific explanation on the origin of earthquakes, an antique vision that established a connection between subterranean winds, storms and seismic waves.

According to Aristotles, and then Lucretius, Seneca and Pliny, winds circulated in the hidden hollows of the earth. Sometimes, winds exerted a mighty pressure on their subterranean abodes, and their oscillating motion generated seismic effects on the surface; sometimes, they even succeeded

in escaping their underground prisons, so giving way to powerful storms which contributed to the overall destruction of the land above.

Fig. 16 - Eerie scenery at today's Lakes of Pilate

So while the men of the Iron Age who lived amid the Apennines had confronted with the frightful seismic waves which recurrently struck their territory by possibly imagining a ghastly dream of demonic gods lurking beneath their mountains, the Greeks and Romans followed an utterly different path, impervious as it was in the lack of any solid scientific foundations, and yet based on fully natural, worldly considerations, with no need to introduce any god or demon: a path that will eventually lead the culture of the Western world to modern science as we know it today. A path that also led, in Roman and medieval times, to the total abandonment of any previous mythical explanation of tremblors as possibly caused by demonic gods supposedly living beneath the ground.

Fig. 17 - Earthquakes and winds from Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis historia* (from the first printed edition, Venice, 1469), p. 20

Memory of all conjectural Sabine and Picene traditions got lost; however, the mythical might of the Sibillini Mountains, fuelled by recursive earthquakes, seems to have persisted across the centuries, attracting extraneous legendary tales with a demonic penchant (Sibyl, Pilate) to these remote peaks. And magical tempests, the classical explanation for earthquakes as found in classical authors, and still associated with both the Cave and the Lake in the renowned medieval legendary complex, might be just the faint legacy of an Iron Age legendary structure which has gone totally lost: the vanishing smoke of a gun that is no longer there.

9. Sibillini Mountain Range: through the narrative layers to the legend's core

The final outcome of our investigation of the legendary tradition which lives amid the cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a remote, craggy territory

set in the Italian central Apennines, is the identification of a potential sedimentation of many different narrative layers.

Our primary starting point was the legendary tale about an Apennine Sibyl. We saw that this Sibyl of the Apennines seems to have come out at the beginning of the fifteenth century, as a shining, lonely star, from a sort of echoing void, an impenetrable mist, from which she began her successful travel into the subsequent ages. No mention of her dwelling amid the Sibillini Mountain Range can be retrieved in earlier centuries.

Fig. 18 - The image we presented in the final paragraph of our previous article *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, with the Sibyl emerging from the mists of time at the beginning of the fifteenth century (composite image by the author)

So the question was: has that Sibyl really journeyed a long way across the centuries and through that inscrutable fog, after having started her travel in ancient times and having remained unseen until she emerged in the fifteenth century? Or, was she the more recent product of some strange condensation of that thick, whirling mist, in which her myth took form not in antiquity, but just very close to the beginning of the fifteenth century?

Did the Apennine Sibyl arise from the condensation of any sort of peculiar nature of that place, the Sibillini Mountain Range, having been subsequently clad with additional mythical themes taken from other tales and stories?

As our research progressed, we found out that we were on the right track. In the light of a closer scrutiny, the true lineage of the Apennine Sibyl started to appear: a Sibyl that comes out from a long, antique tradition concerning Morgan le Fay and the chivalric tales which are part of the Matter of Britain, with the character of 'Sebile', friend and companion to Morgan, filling the void in the centuries which precede the fourteenth.

Fig. 19 - The previous image now completed with the footsteps left by the Sibyl as Morgan's companion (composite image by the author)

So the methodology to be applied in the unfolding of the mysterious origin of the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tradition became clear: all literary additions conferred to Cave's and Lake's legendary tales throughout the centuries were to be identified and removed, so as to take

off all the concentric layers and sheltering leaves that encircle and suffocate the true mythical nucleus, with the aim of cleaning the original mythical core by wiping out the narrative elements that have been added with time to the real story: narrative elements that were borrowed from several different mythical tales across the centuries and the millennia.

In the following diagram, we set out the amazing, fascinating superposition of narrative layers that insists on the original legendary core which seems to live in the Sibillini Mountain Range, a core which in our research is conjecturally connected to the peculiar seismic character of this territory.

Fig. 20 - Sibillini Mountain Range, the superposition of legendary layers as identified and conjectured in the research elaborated by Michele Sanvico in recent years

In our exploration of the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range, we have stumbled upon layers and layers of additional material: literary elements pertaining to different legendary traditions and tales which seem to have been superimposed to a basic mythical core connected to the presence of a sinister Cave and Lake in the area of the Sibillini Mountains.

The first, top-level layer pertains to the local, naive folk tales concerning dancing fairies with goat-like legs who used to dance at night with the local peasants and shepherds: simple tales, not dissimilar from many other narratives which can be found in the Italian Alps or other areas of the Apennine ridge, and were reported to philologists Gaston Paris and Pio Rajna during their visit to the Sibillini Mountain Range by the poor inhabitants of Castelluccio di Norcia and Pretare in 1897.

Beneath this very simple sort of local tales, of more recent origin and known to local residents even in our present age, we find the medieval legendary layers concerning the presence of a dwelling for an Apennine Sibyl and a burial place for Roman prefect Pontius Pilate.

As we could see earlier in this same papers, the presence of a medieval legendary layer enshrouding the narratives about the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate just cannot be denied: the touch of the characters belonging to the Matter of Britain, Morgan le Fay and Sebile, is manifest on the Sibyl's hidden realm, making it a superimposed narrative which is derived from a northern-European legendary tradition concerning magical castles and mountains, and featuring as main characters the necromantic figures of King Arthur's half-sister and her companion Sebile; and, in a same way, the main elements of Pontius Pilate's medieval tale are patently visible, being manifestly this second legend an Italian version of the well-known medieval narrative on Pontius Pilate and his cursed corpse, a tale which has established an abode into a small Lake nested within the crests of Mount Vettore. Both tales are to be considered as extraneous, overlaid legends of foreign origin which found, for reasons connected to the necromantic traits of the place, a suitable abode in this specific area.

When we stop focusing on the figures of the Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate, both belonging to a lore which is extraneous to this portion of the Italian territory, we begin to be able to consider different aspects of the legends of the Cave and Lake. Aspects that they have in common. Specific

traits that both of them seem to share. Following the identification of the listed additional legendary layers, we could easily spot the subsequent layer: a layer which seems to point to the original traits that, according to the available sources, mark the tales of the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake. Both legends feature a number of common aspects, including the performance of necromantic rituals, the presence of legendary fiendish beings, and devastations arising from both sites.

And another common trait marks both sites sitting in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range: an otherworldly character, which is found in literature when passageways to the a realm of dead or demons are described, from Vergil's *Aeneid* to the *Visio Sancti Pauli Apostoli*, the *Dialogues* written by Pope St. Gregory the Great, and up to the visits to the Christian Hell elaborated by the Irish tradition, with the legend of St. Patrick's Purgatory as the culminating point of a narrative path which has lasted for more than a thousand years.

What is to be retrieved beneath this ghastly, obscure layer?

Fig. 21 - Italy and the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Apennine ridge

According to the original conjecture set out by Michele Sanvico, we possibly find the primeval layer, the legendary core which was so powerful as to attract to the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range a number of different tales from various sources across Europe. As we explained earlier

in the present paper, this mighty core might be connected to the peculiar seismic character of this portion of land, and with the conjectural presence, in times as far in the past as the Iron Age, of a demonic worship linked to earthquakes and the way to placate them. A founding layer that got lost already in Roman times, with their prescientific explanations for the tremblings of the earth, which were reputed to be caused by the pressure exerted by subterranean winds, sometimes erupting on the surface in the form of storms.

Layer by layer, leave by leave, we have unfolded the antique literary envelope which for centuries has concealed the true likeness of the Apennine Sibyl. A disentanglement process that started from the additional layers of medieval origin which narrate of a Sibyl and a Roman prefect, and then proceeded back in time, to the real, deepest core of the legend.

In the above framework, the goal to uncover the true essence of the myth of the Apennine Sibyl, the inner core of her ancient legend, seems to have been possibly achieved. We have removed all literary additions conferred to her legendary tale across the centuries. We have taken off all the concentric layers that encircle and suffocate her true mythical nucleus, the way a rose is deprived of the outer petals which shelter the fragrant redolence of its central heart. We have cleaned her figure by wiping out the narrative elements that have been added with time to her story, borrowed from several different mythical tales. We have stripped all her disguises off so as to be able to see her true, antique semblance.

For the first time after centuries, through a cloudy and apparently inscrutable fog, consisting of foreign tales which tell stories of Sibyls and Roman prefects, we have started to get glimpses of the true, common core of both legends. A core that is possibly connected to the deepest fears of human soul: the fear of death, the fear of chthonian potencies, the fear of earthquakes.

In 2019, three years after a most destructive seismic wave which struck the Sibillini Mountain Range and its inhabitants, a man was interviewed by ANSA Italian news agency. He was an elderly man who used to live in Castelluccio di Norcia, a settlement that was entirely demolished by the terrific earthquakes.

And the words he uttered, though spoken by contemporary lips, were thoroughly impressive:

«... Suddenly, a Fiend arrives from underneath», he said, «and tears down everything» (in the original Italian words: «... poi arriva il Diavolo sotto, e sfascia tutto»).

A Fiend arrives, from beneath. And devastates the whole land.

The Iron Age, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, suddenly seems to reach out to us through an unfathomable span of time: on the eerie, divine, terrifying waves of earthquakes.

Michele Sanvico